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To cite this article: Kristoffer Kloch *et al* 2025 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **3123** 012045

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Enabling an AUTonomous and FLEXible hinterland transport ecosystem: Main modal shift issues and potential transport solutions

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Abstract. While autonomous ships are said to be an enabler for modal shift in Europe, they require a broader transformation of the transport and business ecosystems to be effective. That is, current logistics paradigms and rapid advancements in zero-emission road transport may inadvertently incentivise a shift away from waterborne transport. This study explores this conundrum, by looking at the role of ports as integrated logistics and energy hubs, the revitalization of abandoned transshipment sites, and the reduction of transport waste as potential solutions. Conceptualizations of novel transport components are proposed, aimed at enhancing the flexibility, sustainability, and efficiency of intermodal transport ecosystems using IWT and thus potentially unlocking progress toward Europe's modal shift goals.

1. Introduction

Despite decades of European policies aiming at shifting freight transport from road to the more sustainable modes rail and waterborne transport [1], [2], no substantial progress has been observed [3]. Policy objectives provide high-level commitments but often fail to translate into enforceable modal shift mandates due to significant differences between EU ambitions and national strategies [4], [5]. Also, modal shift is inconsistently framed in policy strategies, which makes the metrics for measuring modal shift misaligned and the accountability of the involved parties inadequate [6]. In addition, modal shift objectives have rarely translated into enforceable obligations [7], with pricing-based incentivisation mechanisms such as carbon taxes [8] and road tolls [9] either insufficient to stimulating an actual modal shift. With societal costs from European road traffic estimated at €820 billion annually [10], and a persistent growth in European transport demand [11], European policymakers are in dire need to turn the tides on modal shift outcomes.

There is a significant potential for modal shift from road to inland waterway transport (IWT) [12], with value propositions centred around lower transport costs, CO₂ emissions and road congestion [13]. However, IWT also has challenges related to unreliable water levels [14], [15], [16] and fragmented hinterland terminal services [17], [18], [19]. While transport cost for IWT relative to road reduces with increasing shipment size and distance, transport time increases, and

frequency reduces [20]. Furthermore, geographical location might imply road transport for first and/or last mile, which negatively affect the competitiveness of IWT [21]. For shorter distances, the result is often that once a container is on a truck, it stays on the truck.

A possible solution might be to extend the reach of IWT towards origins and destinations of cargo through small ships that can operate on larger parts of the waterways, thus reducing the need for last-mile truck haulage [22]. However, this could also result in higher transport cost, which may explain the rarity of small ships in the current IWT fleet [23]. The question is then if smaller ships could be designed in a way that reduces cost and increases revenue. A potential solution to this challenge can be found in automation as it can enable uncrewed ships, which are currently under development [22], [24], [25], [26]. Uncrewed ships are projected to significantly reduce costs [27], [28], [29], and enable increased space for cargo [23], [30].

However, small autonomous ships alone will not usher a renaissance of IWT. As smaller waterways in Europe are rarely used for cargo transport, the associated transport infrastructure and business ecosystem would need adaptations to allow for both modal shift in general and autonomous shipping in particular [31]. This includes the development of innovative energy, transshipment and cargo consolidation solutions that can revitalise some of the heterogeneously available infrastructure on the European inland waterways [32]. The contribution of this paper is thus to identify the main challenges and propose consequent innovative solutions that will accelerate the modal shift through an expansion of IWT by using abandoned, underutilised or entirely new transport locations on the inland waterways of Europe.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The study applies a research design inspired by the Double-Diamond framework. Figure 1 illustrate this design, consisting both of diverging (i.e. “broadening”) and converging (i.e. “narrowing”) phases that aims to discover and define the “issues”, as mentioned, in the Problem Space and subsequently provide conceptual solutions to these “issues” in the Solution Space. The framework has been used to identify issues and propose conceptual solutions pertaining to a sustainable waterborne logistics ecosystem through the following phases: First, the Discover phase involved an expansive desk research, including review of academic literature, public data and industry reports, to Discover the systemic barriers facing both shipping and logistics in a

Figure 1. Research Design of this study (inspired by the Double Diamond framework)

broader sense, and IWT in a narrower sense. Second, the Define phase involved synthesising these scattered insights into specific problem statements. The outcomes of the first and second phases are documented in section 3. Third, the Develop phase dived into the problem statements to develop, or identify, key requirements for potential solutions, drawing on best practices, stakeholder co-creation and scenario-based thinking in concurrent workshops. Fourth, the Deliver phase involved narrowing down possible solutions, based on the requirements, into conceptual ideas that could be implemented. The outcomes of the third and fourth phases are documented in section 4.

2.2 Research Methods

A multi-method approach has been applied in this study, combining desk research and workshops while grounding the methods in a specific use case investigation. These methods play different roles across the phases of the double diamond framework.

Desk research is the systematic collecting and synthesizing of existing information, including but not limited to academic literature, industry reports, and market data, to generate insights without collecting new primary data. Thus, desk research has been used to understand existing issues pertaining to sustainable logistics, which has subsequently been used to frame the workshops: to ask the right questions, challenge assumptions and define meaningful design goals.

Workshops From January 2025 - June 2025, the study has employed a dual workshop format to explore challenges and potential solutions. An online weekly workshop series with a focused group of participants (the authors) facilitated agile and creative brainstorming that enable the generation, and iterative refinement of ideas across the identified problematic themes. Complementing these sessions, three physical workshops were held, bringing together the entirety of the AUTOFLEX project consortium [33], including logistics companies, research institutes, energy providers, technology developers and port authorities, to engage in structured discussion. These physical workshops followed a clearly defined agenda in which the identified themes in the problem and solution spaces from the online workshops were presented, scrutinised, debated and further developed.

3. The Problem Space

The widely used “5-lever decarbonisation framework” outline five key levers for decarbonising shipping [34] and logistics [35]: freight demands; transport modes; asset utilisation; energy efficiency and zero-emission energy. This study focusses on promoting the choice of transport modes, i.e. modal shift, and try to incentivise that choice through the remaining levers. While energy efficiency is studied in parallel [39], [40], [41], this study specifically examines freight demands (or rather freight concentration), zero-emission energy and asset utilisation.

3.1 Economies of scale, cargo centralisation and modal shift towards road transport

The pursuit of lower transport costs per unit has driven carriers to invest in increasing larger “mega ships” paired with redistribution via hub-and-spoke feeder networks [39]. While these mega ships are more cost-efficient per transported unit from both investment [40] and operational [41] perspectives, their viability is highly sensitive to utilisation rates as operations below full capacity quickly leads to diseconomies of scale and a consequent unfeasibility of the concept [42], [43]. Although economies of scale do exist, they tend to plateau or even reverse with too large ship sizes due to port inefficiencies and operational rigidity [44], [45]. Moreover, environmental and logistical challenges further undermine the long-term cost-effectiveness of mega-ships for global supply chains more broadly [42], [46].

The economic pressure to fill these mega ships has subsequently driven carriers to form

strategic alliances which roughly account for around 90% of global TEU [47], [48]. These alliances allow carriers to share ship space, coordinate schedules, and reduce duplication of routes, effectively turning rivals into collaborators to maximize ship utilisation and maintain service frequency [49]. That is, without these alliances, no single carrier could simultaneously fill their mega ships and meet customer demand for service frequency [42]. However, this tendency also reduces market diversity and competitiveness, as smaller carriers are increasingly pushed to the margins or into subordinate roles within global shipping networks [50]. The resulting oligopolistic market structures obscure actual competition, raise concerns over potential price manipulation and challenge regulatory frameworks aimed at preserving a level playing field [40].

The rise of mega-ships has also concentrated transport flows into a limited number of global mega-ports, as only ports with sufficient capital and space to invest in the required dredging, infrastructure, machinery etc., have been able to keep up [42], [51]. While modern ports continue to upgrade to meet the demands of containerisation and increasingly larger ships, these capital-intensive adaptations are not universally accessible and deepen inequality between ports and across the global shipping network, with only the wealthiest ports surviving [42]. Also, due to the high fixed operational costs of mega ships and the need to keep service schedules, mega ships limit their port calls and thus further marginalise secondary ports and regions that have been omitted although potentially having made the necessary upgrades to accommodate the ships [52]. All this leads to increasingly concentrated cargo volumes and shipping routes, creating systemic dependence of a few mega-sized strategic ports [53], [54].

Small-to-medium-sized ports (SMPs), particularly inland and regional terminals, often lack the financial muscle-power to remain viable in the hub-and-spoke networks mandated by mega-ships [55], [56], [57]. Consequently, shipping's contribution to global trade and development, reflected in the UNCTAD connectivity index, continues to decline [42], [58]. This marginalisation also undermines modal shift towards waterborne modalities by sidelining regional or inland ports and increasing reliance on road freight to bridge the distance to distant mega-hubs [59], [60], [61]. That is, as the heterogenous pool of waterborne actors slowly disappears, fewer viable waterborne transport alternatives exist, which in turn leads to a modal shift away from waterborne transport [62], [63]. SMPs thus face a widening gap between core and peripheral infrastructure as the upgrades needed to stay competitive remain out of reach [64], [65]. In the context of IWT, infrastructure conditions is a key factor shaping both the opportunities and challenges of sustainable IWT [66], and hence, the poor infrastructure conditions currently available in most inland terminals hinder their development into thriving logistics hubs, thereby at least partly impeding progress on European modal shift ambitions [62], [67], [68].

In summary, the dominance of mega-ships, strategic alliances, and capital-intensive infrastructure requirements has led to a highly centralised waterborne transport ecosystem wherein SMPs, especially those on inland waterways, are becoming increasingly marginalised due to concentrated cargo flows, limited service diversity, and reinforced geographic and economic disparities. This in turn undermines European modal shift ambitions. As these trends harden into structural barriers, there is an urgent need for solutions that can reintegrate SMPs, especially those on the inland waterways, into the global transport ecosystem. Consequently, innovative terminal concepts must be explored that offer scalable and adaptable solutions capable of revitalising the role of SMPs, especially along underutilised inland corridors.

3.2 From Single to Dual Roles: Ports as transshipment and energy hubs enabling renewable modal shift

As gateways to international trade, ports have the capacity to influence the adoption of renewable fuels and play a pivotal role in aligning regional actors and operations with broader climate targets [69]. For instance, initiatives like green shipping corridors require the active involvement of ports to provide the physical, operational and regulatory conditions necessary for sustainable shipping

practices [70]. Without proactive port involvement, shipowners face barriers in accessing new fuels, thereby slowing progress across the entire supply chain [71]. Therefore, ports are not passive observers but crucial enablers in shaping the future of sustainable logistics.

Ports have slowly evolved from being viewed as primarily public entities that promote regional development via accessible infrastructure to quasi-private actors providing commercial services in a competitive environment [72]. This requires ports to strategically adapt their operations, services and activities to differentiate themselves and enhance how they create and capture value [72]. Ports are no longer just enablers of trade, but active participants in the creation and management of logistics, including provision of renewable energy, transshipment with zero-emission machinery and integration into logistics corridors, and actively influencing how shipping networks are formed [73], [74], [75]. Thus, ports are transforming into heterogeneous business hubs that offer a diverse set of services at independent, bilateral and ecosystem levels to support the development of the port itself and the economic activity in its vicinity [76]. The conceptualisation of ports as energy hubs that increasingly import, produce, store and distribute renewable energy has gained traction [77]. Many ports are positioning themselves as renewable energy gateways that enable zero-emissions supply chains in an effort to get a competitive advantage [78]. This includes forging strategic alliances with actors across existing and future renewable energy value chains to ensure their own and their region's competitiveness long-term [79]. Ports are also taking an active role as experimental hubs for new energy and logistics innovations, creating testbeds for companies to test sustainable technologies and operations [80].

As renewable fuels diversify (hydrogen, ammonia, methanol etc.), ports must choose between specialising in a single fuel type and thus limiting commercial relationships with some ship operators, or capitalising on several options and thus increasing capital expenditures and possible port inefficiencies (see e.g. [81], [82], [83], [84], [85]). The dilemma is exacerbated by mutual dependence between ports and shipowners as each relies on the other to realise the value of the new fuel(s) [81], [83]. Furthermore, ports must adapt to mitigate the instability in energy demands combined with the intermittent nature of renewable energies [86], ideally through multi-energy systems combining solar, wind, batteries and e.g. hydrogen to enable both immediate use, storage and overall energy elasticity [87]. Key infrastructure sectors, such as energy providers, are often viewed as natural monopolies due to their critical role and systemic significance for the economy and society, and are thus subject to economic regulation [88]. As ports take on greater energy-focused roles, new legal, financial and commercial frameworks are needed [89]. Emerging governance strategies highlight the importance of cross-sectoral integration of energy, logistics and digitalisation for enabling multimodal decarbonisation [90]. Yet, despite their growing importance in the energy market, most ports lack comprehensive energy management strategies, although such strategies help ports benefit from improved efficiency, new revenue streams and strengthen competitiveness in an increasingly sustainability-focused marketplace [91].

SMPs, however, face unique and compounding challenges in the transition to logistics and energy hubs. Due to their lower trade volumes and consequent range of operational, financial and environmental disadvantages compared to the mega ports [92], SMPs often lack the technical capacity, financial resources and institutional support to implement decarbonisation measures and invest in renewable energy for own terminal operations or for supply to ships, trucks or trains [93], [94], [95]. Consequently, SMPs adopt only limited sustainability measures or remain inactive entirely [56], [96]. Furthermore, SMPs typically share infrastructure such as power grids and bunkering stations with adjacent industrial facilities, making their transition highly dependent on shared assets, inter-sectoral linkages and location-specific factors such as local topography, resource availability etc. [97]. To overcome (some of) these barriers, SMPs increasingly collaborate with larger ports nearby and seek to leverage unique advantages such as surplus land, specialised infrastructure or strong regional industry links [55], [77], [98]. Regional industries

may simultaneously benefit from the spillover effects from waterborne transport development, especially on the inland waterways [99].

In summary, the transformation of ports into energy-integrated logistics hubs, a crucial component in decarbonising global supply chains and logistics ecosystems, is reshaping the sector. However, SMPs remain sidelined, which undermines not only regional economic equity, but also broader climate and modal shift goals such as the revitalisation of European IWT. To address this, there is a pressing need for innovative terminal concepts that combine energy production, storage and delivery with cargo handling in modular and scalable formats. Such terminal concepts should enable SMPs to re-integrate into sustainable transport chains and revitalise inland waterways as viable transport alternative within the Europe's logistics ecosystem.

3.3 Systemic transport waste from suboptimal utilisation of cargo units

In Europe, 21.8% of total road freight vehicle kilometres carry nothing, with a significant discrepancy between empty kilometres in national transport (25.9) compared to international transport (13.1%) [100]. When comparing non-empty trip average loads with the average capacity of truck weights classifications (extrapolated In Europe, 21.8% of total road freight vehicle kilometres carry nothing, with a significant discrepancy between empty kilometres in national transport (25.9) compared to international transport (13.1%) [100]. When comparing non-empty trip average loads with the average capacity of truck weights classifications (extrapolated from [100] & [101]), load utilisation per loaded trip is around 75.0%, meaning that 25% of trailer space remains unused. Thus, when factoring in both empty trips and unused spaced in non-empty trips, system-wide utilisation drops to around 59%, highlighting major inefficiencies in European freight transport. However, do note that the data in [100] & [101] is given in weights and not in volumes. Given that some commodities may use 100% of the volume capacity of a truck transport, but not its weight capacity, the above inferences on trailer utilisation should be used with caution.

This underutilisation extends beyond road transport, as waterborne transport also suffers from empty or partially loaded containers, although precise utilisation percentages are difficult to measure due to limited data availability [34]. For empty shipping containers, repositioning is in itself an area of research with numerous methods, models, and applications [102]. The costs of repositioning empty containers in the global shipping network are estimated at 15-20 billion USD per year on average, representing 5-8% of total operating costs for most carriers [103]. These inefficiencies mainly stem from imbalances in traffic flows on most trade routes. For example, on Asia-Europe trade routes, 16.1 million TEU are moved westwards whereas "only" 6.9 million TEU moved eastwards (a 2.33 : 1.00 ratio) in 2024 [104]. Within Europe, similar imbalances are observed between flow ratios (import : export) and fill rates (loaded : empty) [105]. In addition to empty container repositioning, waterborne transport also experiences issues with partly-filled transport units. For instance, for US-imports in 2018, only 64.4% of containers declared as "Full-Container-Load" (FCL) were actually full, meaning that 35.6% of the declared containers were in fact "Less-Than-a-Container-Load (LCL)" [106].

Improved cargo consolidation of both transport assets (ships) and transport units (trailers/containers) is key to improve the utilisation of logistics resources and thus the environmental impact of supply chains [107]. However, the competitiveness of waterborne transport depends heavily on high and balanced utilisation, as road transport can more easily outcompete and optimise on return routes with marginal costs [108]. Consequently, not all modes can consolidate with the same ease. While consolidation in IWT can reduce transport inefficiencies, it is dependent on a strategic hinterland placement on the convergence of large cargo flows [109]. Even then, the approach is only feasible if the majority of the eligible containers

are LCLs and if transshipment costs are kept to an absolute minimum (*ibid.*). The relocation of cross-docking operations to port areas can enhance efficiency, reduce emissions and improve hinterland container utilisation, but the performance of consolidation strategies must be tailored to the shipment distance, cargo type, load factor, urgency and the proportion of LCLs [110]. However, the poor operational and commercial coordination that exist between barge operators and deep-sea terminal operators today may keep hinterland consolidation efforts futile if structural changes are not made [111]. In urban logistics, consolidation centres are seen as vital for sustainable city distribution [112], [113], yet they remain poorly implemented in reality [114], [115]. Municipalities are increasingly deploying financial and regulatory measures such as subsidies and mandatory use of consolidation centres to incentivize greener urban logistics [116].

However, consolidated transport also has drawbacks. First, it requires time to gather cargo asynchronously, complicating consolidated just-in-time (JIT) deliveries [117]. Second, delivery speed and reliability often depend on service type (e.g. same day vs. deferred deliveries), with faster options normally not permitting consolidation delays (*ibid.*). Third, given that value and time-criticality differ between commodity classifications [118], consolidation may be more feasible for homogenous goods, making it difficult to consolidate heterogeneous flows of goods in general.

In summary, low utilisation of transport assets and units across modalities reveals major inefficiencies in the European logistics ecosystem, increasing emissions and inflating costs. While cargo consolidation is crucial, especially for sustainable modes like waterborne transport with limited backhaul options, it often fails due to infrastructural, temporal, and commercial challenges. Consequently, there is a need to explore new forms of consolidation concepts that go beyond traditional cross-docking models, potentially enabling multiple transport customers to share segmented container space at the point of loading and unloading.

4. The Solution Space

Section 3 discussed the barriers to sustainable logistics in the broad sense and modal shift in particular, and identified three main problem areas; the centralisation of cargo flows around large seaports that accommodates increasingly larger ocean-going ships and has led to modal shift towards road; the urgent need for sea and inland ports to adopt a pivotal role in enabling shipping sector decarbonisation and the risk for energy centralisation unless solutions supporting SMPs are found; and widespread inefficiencies due to underutilised transport capacity of IWT increasing emissions and cost. To overcome these problems, this section first derives requirements that solutions must meet, and then, proposes a set of innovative, modular conceptualizations to revitalise abandoned or underutilised SMPs, support the transition toward zero-emission IWT, and improve load factor performance of waterborne container transport. Together, these conceptualizations represent an intertwined solution space aimed at making the logistics ecosystems of the future an “even playing field”.

4.1 How to revitalise and reintegrate unused terminal infrastructure and SMPs into the transport ecosystem?

The consequence of a highly centralised waterborne transport is that there is no to extremely limited use of old transshipment infrastructure. In many European cities, former transshipment locations in the city centre have been abandoned and replaced with new and larger terminals at the outskirts of the agglomeration, so that there is (nearly) no transshipment activity left in the city centres (see e.g. the cases of Gothenburg [119], Southampton [119], Rotterdam [119][120], Cagliari [121], Catania [121] and Trieste [121]). Consequently, waterborne transport is moving to the larger terminal locations outside of the cities, with the side effect that cargo is being delivered by truck into the city centres and other consignees close to water. This subsequently causes

congestion effects on the road network and significant external costs to cities and societies [10]. While numerous structurally sound but unused quays and infrastructures remains [32], cargo owners have increasingly limited waterborne services, as no routes are going to these abandoned terminals, leaving the cargo owner to utilise roadborne transport as the only existing option.

While small autonomous ships offer a significant potential to revert these tendencies (see Section 1), they will only be able to capitalise on their potential if transshipment locations are also activated as well. This is of major significance as only then smaller waterways can be served, and a sufficiently large network coverage with by new transport services can be offered. Re-establishing transshipment at such unused quays along the inland waterways can be achieved through diverse measures, either on the shoreside or aboard autonomous ships. One could imagine that a solution would be ships with their own onboard cargo handling equipment. However, there are several issues that prevent that as an option, especially for small ships. Firstly, onboard cranes would require space and thus reduce cargo capacity, secondly, stability would be difficult to achieve for small ships since the handling of high weight cargo units, like a container, will cause huge moments that will lead to the capsizing of the ship. Finally, even if stability issues could be solved, some handling equipment on the quay would be needed anyway as containers are typically destined to somewhere else than on the quay. In summary, carrying onboard cranes on small ships would hamper their competitiveness, and most likely some quay side equipment would still be needed.

The other option is then to develop terminal infrastructure to enable the transshipment of cargo at these formerly used infrastructural sites. However, the challenge is that establishing a traditional terminal is expensive and typically implies investment in permanent infrastructure. Which implies a need for significant cargo volumes for a longer period. Otherwise, the investment risk would be too high. To reduce the investment risk, what is needed is infrastructure that has minimal investment requirements and which, ideally, can be relocated at a relatively low cost. What is needed is a “terminal-as-a-service” concept where the terminal is mobile in the sense that it is semi-permanent but relocatable such that it can be established somewhere else.

This need spawned the idea of the Temporary Port Terminals (TPTs) concept. The TPTs should be flexible and modular logistics nodes designed to enable cargo handling in underutilised, constrained, or non-permanent locations. Unlike traditional terminals, TPTs needs to be able to rapidly deploy, tailored to specific operational contexts, and particularly suited to environments where building permanent terminals is not of interest. The TPTs would need to provide three core functions: cargo handling, cargo storage, and terminal access and security. Each core function is discussed in the following with several possible realisations that can be combined in any shape of form to ensure that the constructed TPT concept is adapted specifically to the context and logistical needs of the use case.

Cargo Handling Equipment (CHE). Refers to the transshipment of cargo for what four possible realisations have been identified: 1) *Fixed ashore CHE* includes cranes on quay-side infrastructure. These solutions provide high lifting capacity and stable operation but are only feasible when basic infrastructure is available. While offering high handling efficiency, fixed ashore CHE often involves significant capital expenditure (CAPEX) and is less suited to temporal setups without prior investment. 2) *Fixed afloat CHE* includes cranes that are mounted on either inland ships or barges. This combination allows repositioning of the CHE along the waterway without reliance on shore-side infrastructure, offering increased flexibility at abandoned or minimally equipped terminals. 3) *Mobile ashore CHE* includes reach stackers or tug masters (for LoLo or RoRo) temporarily stationed quayside, with potential relocation opportunities to other terminals or TPTs. Their free

mobility makes them well-suited for TPTs that rely on repurposed or abandoned infrastructure. 4) *Mobile afloat CHE* includes reach stackers or tug masters (for LoLo or RoRo) residing onboard a floating barge or the inland ship itself. These units disembark and conduct transshipment operations on land, which allows for flexibility and independence from local infrastructure.

Cargo Storage Area (CSA). Refers to the storage of cargo (and equipment) for what three realisations have been identified: 1) *On-quay CSA* uses terminal space in a traditional manner and offers efficient cargo operations. However, this setup may become problematic when throughput increases, as spatial congestion and conflicts with other uses of quay infrastructure (e.g., public spaces) can limit operational scalability. 2) *Floating CSA* uses floating barges moored alongside the quay for storage capacity, which allows cargo to be handled asynchronously from ship schedules. This setup is valuable when quay space is limited or in sensitive urban zones or heritage sites, where infrastructure upgrades are undesirable. 3) *Remote CSA* uses offsite warehouses or repurposed lots when storage is not otherwise available. These configurations involve internal transport coordination to move cargo between the quay and the remote CSA, with overall efficiency contingent on the distance and seamlessness of this transport.

Terminal Access and Security (TAS). Refers to the terminal controls for what three realisations have been identified: 1) *Open TAS* offers a basic control level, relying on informal spatial demarcation without fencing or security personnel. While its strength lies in easy and flexible implementability, its drawback lies in potential theft or vandalism, making it relevant only for low-risk and low-value cargoes. 2) *Limited TAS* offers a moderate control level, relying on physical barriers already in place at the transshipment site. Outside access is managed, relying on predictability and cooperation with municipal authorities, which suits cargo types where full ISPS compliance is unnecessary. 3) *ISPS-compliant TAS* offers a high control level and is fully compliant with the ISPS Code. It includes controlled entry, secure fencing, surveillance and formal security protocols, making it ideal for cargoes of high-risk and value, but requires more time, investment and coordination with authorities.

4.2 *How to enable renewable energy sources in the IWT transport ecosystem through ports, including SMPs?*

Ships must transition to zero-emission technologies to be a sustainable transport alternative. This requires zero-emission propulsion technologies using renewable energy sources. Which in turn creates a need for this renewable energy to be available in ports. However, centralisation of energy availability would further solidify the centralisation of cargo flows. One could easily imagine that “energy-of-scale” with a lot of energy being produced in big ports, but nowhere else, could become a similar issue as the “economy-of-scale” induced concentration of cargo flows. To revert the economy-of-scale’s direction of cargo and service concentration in larger transport hubs, a simultaneous and associated renaissance in the energy supply and distribution to the waterborne transport system is needed. Thus, to extend the range of IWT, SMPs will play a critical role, because if renewable energy is only available in the big ports, a zero-emission IWT ecosystem will have a shorter range compared to the current state of the art, since batterie propelled ships, implied limited range and a need for frequent replenishment. And if IWT ranges are relatively short, the model shift becomes further challenging from a cost-perspective, because transshipment costs will take up a higher share of the total transport costs. This may lead cargo owners to choose a road borne transport service where transshipments are not an issue, keeping costs down, instead of a waterborne alternative. Hence, most, if not all, ports need to move towards a dual role as logistics and energy service providers, especially with focus on renewable energies-The ports’ energy strategies will thus become fundamental enablers for green IWT.

Thus, there is a need to develop scalable port setups that enable terminals and ports to deliver both transshipment, logistics and energy provision services – particularly in SMPs to extend IWT range and decentralise cargo flows away from the larger ports. This is not about taking business away from the larger ports; it is about decongestion the roads around the ports and allowing the larger ports to focus on their primary value gain: integrating with transoceanic seagoing ships. If SMPs can produce and sell energy, this may create additional revenue streams that helps in making their revitalising economically and commercially feasible. This need resulted in the idea of the Cargo and Energy Terminal (CET) concept. The CET concept envisions inland terminals as hybrid energy and logistics hubs designed to advance the decarbonisation and decentralisation of freight transport. The CET would need to provide four core functions: cargo handling, renewable energy production, battery-based storage, and modular charging infrastructure. These four functions would enable CETs to support electric driven inland ships, vehicles, and terminal operations, while reducing grid dependency and unlocking new energy-service roles. Especially in small-to-medium-sized inland ports, CETs offer a transformative blueprint to reinsert these terminals into a greener logistics network, positioning them as critical actors in Europe’s modal shift strategy and its transition toward energy-resilient, low-emission freight corridors.

Two realisation forms of renewable energy production at CETs have been identified:

Wind-derived energy production (WEP). Refers to the installation of wind turbines within or adjacent to port terminal sites to generate renewable electricity. With high spatial and capital demands, WEP systems often require long-term investment horizons, which limits their deployment to locations with sufficient spatial and economic viability. WEP plays a critical role in creating energy autonomy and enabling the zero-emission energy usage on terminals, ships and last-mile vehicles.

Solar-derived Energy Production (SEP). Refers to the deployment of photovoltaic systems, typically installed as ground arrays or canopy structures. SEP require lower financial and regulatory burdens compared to WEP, and thus they provide an accessible entry point for CETs transitioning toward partial energy self-sufficiency. SEP also offer operational flexibility, allowing for scalable implementation on constrained sites and integration into existing terminal layouts. In order to utilize renewable produced energy, the following three conceptual solutions have been identified:

Charging Stations (CSs). Refers to the critical interface that connects renewable energy generation to the transport ecosystem. CSs enable the charging of BCs to be used for terminals, ships and last-mile vehicles. CSs use either locally produced energy (via WEP or SEP) or energy from the external grid, though the latter is less desirable vis-à-vis the energy independence goal. Functionally, CSs are pivotal in enabling energy decoupling between consumption and production.

Battery Containers (BCs). Refers to mobile, swappable energy storage units housed in standardised shipping containers that store electricity for flexible deployment across the transport ecosystem. BCs serve dual purposes: powering terminal equipment, inland ships and/or last-mile vehicles. Their modularity enables energy to be decoupled from production location and time, a key component of scalable electrification of temporally retrofitted environments e.g. through energy-as-a-service.

Cargo Handling Equipment (CHE): The operational equipment, such as quay crane, reach stackers, tug masters etc., required to transfer cargo between ships, terminals, storage areas, and last-mile vehicles. The electrification of CHE is an essential aspect of CETs and thus the effective deployment of CHE determines not only operational throughput but also the environmental performance of the entire CET blueprint and the transport ecosystem which it is part of.

4.3 How to enable part-load consolidation concepts that go beyond traditional cross-docking models?

The consequence of the noticeable waste in the utilisation of transport assets and units is increased congestion from transports that could have otherwise been avoided through smarter cargo consolidation schemes. Not only would this decrease the emissions attributable to the transport sector, it would arguably also lower the costs for the transport customers, i.e. freight forwarders and/or cargo owners. Consequently, this suboptimal utilisation of both assets and units further exacerbates the congestion issues discussed in section 4.1. In order to be competitive with road transport, IWT needs to approximate the service depth of road transport. While only a confined set of cargo types and categories are typically transported over water, a larger market segment could be addressed in case intermodal transport concepts with involvement of IWT manage to adopt some of the essential service characteristics of road transport. Hence, a set of dimensions was found pertaining to this conundrum, both pointing towards the same sort of solution.

First, inland ships have historically almost exclusively serviced a single customer (a practice still dominant in today's bulk segment). In convoys (push, tow or coupled), a single ship with different barges could service different customer (i.e. one customer per barge), but for cargo ship in general, the concept of booking "less-than-a-vessel-load" (LVL) is a recent development. The adoption of the standardised shipping container has played a significant role in this shift, enabling IWT to transition from homogenous cargoes in bulk to heterogenous cargoes in various volumes. Comparable capacity-sharing models exist in road transport, namely "full-truck-load" (FTL) and "less-than-full-truck-load" (LTL). Whereas FTL offers simpler, faster and cheaper operations for a single customer, LTL incurs a significant cost-increase if not consolidated with other LTLs to create FTL transport. However, this requires a coordinated effort with additional pick-up, delivery, sorting, and, potentially, cross-docking, which may further increase the transport costs. In ocean shipping, the same capacity-sharing concept is found in "full-container-loads" (FCL) and "less-than-container-loads" (LCL). Naturally, FCL is associated with various benefits, such as greater security due to fewer people accessing the transport unit, faster customs clearance with only one customer involved, and a swifter and more flexible loading and sealing process (even at the consignor's premises) and cost-efficiency. LCL, on the contrary, combines partial loads of different customers and, hence, requires their collection at a dedicated space at which the consolidation towards a full container can take place. Typically, this happens in so-called container freight stations (CFS), often situated in large seaports. These CFS are the sorting centres of incoming and outgoing cargo flows – from both the waterside and the landside. This additional step causes additional effort and costs for the port operators whereas the individual customer will benefit from decreased costs related to the cost used capacity. Whereas LTL is capacity-sharing at both transport asset (truck) and unit (trailer) level, given that trucks rarely carry more than a single trailer, LVL is capacity-sharing at the transport asset (ship) level and the LCL is capacity-sharing at the transport unit (container) level. Therefore, in the context of autonomous ships as enablers of modal shift, furthering these capacity-sharing concepts could potentially enable the inland (autonomous) ship to compete with roadborne transport at the asset utilisation level – especially if the inland ships becomes significantly smaller in size, increasing the range of the IWT network. That is, because most truck units are not fully utilised (see section 3.3), the majority of roadborne transports is arguably LTLs, and by moving the IWT services into the capacity-sharing "domain" at a unit level, e.g. LCL, there may be an argument for fully fledged competition with roadborne modalities. However, in order to convert some of this LTL cargo, the autonomous IWT concept ideally (a) allows for seamless pick-up and delivery of goods from/to customers, (b) involves cost-effective bundling, sorting, and cross-docking steps, when relevant, and (c) fulfils existing constraints of waterborne transport. This may require innovations where transport units (and assets) are incorporating cargo consolidation into their designs.

Second, most bundled LTL services are made possible today by an in-field orchestrator: the truck drivers themselves, who combine multiple functions in their role as they take responsibility for several tasks that are essential for last mile cargo distribution and consolidation. In the absence of this human oversight, an intermodal transport service configuration including autonomous IWT needs to employ solutions which address all of these functions – either in the form of infrastructure, equipment, organization, and/or regulations. Should any of these constraints of typical freight transport be violated in the new service configuration, the economic model and overall viability of LVL services could be undermined. This may compel customers to book full transport units regardless of actual demand, introducing further inefficiencies and unnecessary capacity waste into supply chains. Therefore, the development of transport system components, such as vehicles, transport units, or service models, that can enforce the fulfilment of the above-mentioned constraints is essential for preserving the economic and environmental benefits of part-load logistics in an autonomous transport future.

Third, decoupling the times of supply and demand has increasingly seen a market with concepts like outsourced storage (i.e., contract logistics), rolling or floating warehouse concepts (using road, rail, and IWT as means to intermediately store cargo and transferring the responsibility and cost to third-party service providers, mainly from the transport and logistics industry) and just-in-time or even just-in-sequence concepts (in which the supplier needs to accommodate all required cargo at his own cost and effort until their respective time of need in the customer's premises). As the trailers are rare to find on inland ships and containers are typically not used for continental transport, waterborne transport is characterized by an integral connection of the propulsion unit and the cargo hold (except for convoys). Hence, a new intermodal service concept with a focus on the LVL market needs to find an effective way to safeguard that decoupling supply and demand is possible. From these decoupling points, to which cargo can be delivered and from which it can be retrieved without compulsory synchronisation, last-mile transport to the actual location of need, i. e., the precise ramp of the pertaining factory or warehouse, can be organised. Experience from other areas of the transport and logistics market, such as the parcel delivery in the B2C segment, proves that even self-organized collection of cargo can be assumed in cases of elevated urgency or moderate effort, such as small transport distances, no major change of transport means required or similar features.

These three requirements sparked the idea of the Mobile Distribution Centre (MDC) concept: a modular transport unit concept designed to enable consolidation of smaller intermodal shipments for SMEs in the age of autonomous waterborne transport. The MDC should function as a standalone, self-contained unit that can be embedded within CETs, TPTs, or used independently across supply chains. Unlike traditional transport units, i.e. the container or the trailer (or equivalents), the MDC should be adaptable to the context in which it is deployed, allowing for multi-actor transport orchestration for intermodal services at industrial level. As such, the MDC becomes much more than “just a box”; it becomes a crucial component in intelligent supply chain orchestration that may enable SMEs to partake in modal shift endeavours. To do this, the MDC would need to be developed around four core pillars: its physical architecture, its cargo types, its logistical deployment and its logistical role. Each of these pillars will be discussed in the following, and can, be configured in a multitude of ways, allowing an MDC tailored to the specific and evolving needs of its users and use cases.

Physical Architecture. Refers to the overall physical structure of the MDC and comes in four possible formats: 1) *Standard container.* MDCs can be retrofitted shipping containers that can easily be handled by existing port and intermodal infrastructure. They could be pre-configured offsite and deployed quickly in plug-and-play logistics operation. 2) *Customized storage formats.* MDC can take the shape of a customized body tailored to the needs of the precise cargo or cargo type they have been designed for. While the effectiveness of such a solution may be higher, the related effort and cost of handling such customized solutions need to be observed carefully. 3)

Floating Barge. MDCs can be floating platforms operating along waterways and deployed at multiple terminal locations to load and unload cargo from and to the autonomous inland ship. Apart from cargo handling equipment, they can also carry onboard sorting and/or storage systems themselves, making them highly flexible and time-independent units. 4) *Autonomous and/or self-propelled vessels.* MDCs can be waterborne drones equipped with automated navigation, allowing them to operate independently along the inland waterways. They offer flexibility in routing and scheduling.

Cargo types. This refers to the different cargo types which are to be accommodated in the MDC and comes in four possible formats: 1) *Parcels / e-commerce items.* As such transport units typical for B2B and B2C require secure, compartmentalized handling systems due to their small size, high frequency, and, possibly, large number. MDCs, thus, must support rapid sorting, scanning, and tracking to meet expectations, making them ideal for urban distribution. 2) *Pallets and crates.* Common in B2B logistics, such as retail restocking or agricultural shipments, they require appropriate lifting and stacking equipment within the MDC, which supports efficient loading and unloading but may require more space. 3) *Reverse logistics / packaging / waste* can be collected for reverse logistics in MDCs. They must be equipped to collect and handle mixed cargo types and support circular logistics but then is a notable service for both private and public actors. 4) *Modular cargo units.* Such units, e. g., standard bins, rolling containers, or boxes, allow MDCs to dynamically consolidate or separate flows while maintaining segmentation of goods. These units enhance interoperability across different transport modes and facilities.

Logistical Deployment. This refers to the location of the MDC in the transport chain and comes in three possible formats: 1) *Fixed-node MDCs.* They are permanently stationed at a strategic location like a port, quay, or urban logistics hub. It serves as a stable transshipment or distribution point, benefiting from established infrastructure, secure energy supply, and consistent cargo flows. 2) *Mobile MDCs.* They travel between predetermined locations, often in shuttle loops and along regular routes, connecting the supply and demand sides with one another, e.g. rural producers with urban receivers. It supports regular, recurring flows and can optimise vehicle utilisation through predictable scheduling. 3) *Temporary MDCs.* They are deployed on demand in response to real-time logistics needs, such as congestion, special events, or temporary disruptions. They offer maximum flexibility and responsiveness, often operating in pop-up or short-notice scenarios.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

This paper investigates the barriers that are hindering an increased modal shift from road to inland waterborne transport. The paper also investigates the possibility of overcoming these barriers through a novel autonomous and flexible hinterland transport ecosystem comprising small autonomous inland ships and novel transport components. The research activities performed in this scope followed the methodology of the double-diamond framework. Within the first diamond, the problem space, the main barriers to modal shift to waterborne transport were discussed and narrowed down to the main problems that would need to be solved to overcome these barriers. Based on that, the second diamond, the solution space, discussed what requirements potential solutions would have to meet, and concluded by proposing conceptualised solution meeting these.

In conclusion, three main barriers that prevent a higher modal share for inland waterborne transport were identified:

1) economies of scale has led to cargo centralisation, marginalisation of small-to-medium-sized ports (SMPs) and a modal shift towards road transport. The barrier of economies of scale, cargo centralisation and modal shift towards road transport manifested in transport concentration in the big ports with capital-intensive infrastructure and bigger ships, marginalising SMPs, especially inland terminals lacking the capacity to compete in global competition [42], [52], [54] and decreasing the utilization of the hinterland waterborne network via smaller ships, which prevents the realisation of modal shift goals [57], [58], [62]

2) the transition to renewable energy will require ports to act as hubs for both cargo and energy services, which creates a risk that “energy of scale” may lead to energy centralisation and further marginalisation of SMPs. The barrier of economies of scale, cargo centralisation and modal shift towards road transport manifested in transport concentration in the big ports with capital-intensive infrastructure and bigger ships, marginalising SMPs, especially inland terminals lacking the capacity to compete in global competition [42], [52], [54] and decreasing the utilization of the hinterland waterborne network via smaller ships, which prevents the realisation of modal shift goals [57], [58], [62]. Ports, especially SMPs and inland terminals, are increasingly expected to support freight decarbonisation, yet face major barriers due to limited financial, technical, and institutional capacity [93], [94], [95]. The interdependence between ports and shipowners in adopting new fuels creates a stalemate [100], [102], while the diversity of renewable fuels and intermittency of energy sources complicate investment and system design [86], [87]. SMPs, in particular, often lack the autonomy and scale to implement comprehensive energy strategies [91].

3) a significant amount of suboptimal utilisation of road cargo assets and units is observed, resulting in a lot of “empty” kilometres and a consequent increase in environmental (and, arguably, financial) impacts. The barrier of suboptimal utilisation of cargo units manifests in underutilised transport capacity, including empty vehicle movements and partially filled cargo units [100], [101]. These issues affect both road and waterborne transport, worsened by trade imbalances and poor coordination [104], [105], [106], leading to higher emissions and increased costs [72].

To overcome these barriers, innovative and modular conceptualisations were proposed:

1) Enabling the revitalisation and reintegration of unused terminal infrastructure and SMPs into the transport system by implementing Temporary Port Terminals (TPTs). TPTs offer a flexible, scalable solution. By decoupling terminal functions from permanent infrastructure, TPTs reduce entry barriers for SMPs, enabling participation in waterborne logistics without major investment. Their modular design suits varied settings where traditional infrastructure is limited by space, cost, or regulation. TPTs can revitalise dormant infrastructure, support temporary logistics, and ease congestion at major ports, redistributing cargo flows and enhancing system resilience. They also align with European modal shift goals by making IWT more viable [62], [67], [68]. However, TPTs require at least minimal navigable infrastructure and supportive regulations, which may be lacking in some areas [66]. While they help SMPs re-enter logistics chains, TPTs do not address market power imbalances from mega-ships and alliances [47], [48], [50]. Without supportive policies or collaborative models, TPTs may struggle to ensure service frequency or cargo volumes. Their temporary nature, though flexible, may hinder integration into stable supply chains unless institutionalised through partnerships or regional planning [64], [65].

2) Enabling renewable energy sources in the IWT transport system through SMPs acting as Cargo and Energy Terminal (CETs). CETs offer a modular and scalable concept that integrates renewable energy generation (e.g., wind, solar), battery storage, and charging infrastructure with cargo operations, enabling gradual energy autonomy. That is, even resource-constrained ports can adopt low-level CETs and scale over time. Mobile battery containers and decentralised charging decouple energy production from consumption, reduce grid reliance and enable flexible energy sharing. CETs thus support terminal electrification and position SMPs as contributors to

regional decarbonisation and modal shift goals [77], [89], [99]. However, CETs are not a universal fix. Their success depends on regulatory support, financing, and regional coordination. Shared infrastructure and inter-sectoral dependencies remain vulnerabilities, especially where industrial and energy assets misalign with port goals [97]. While CETs reduce reliance on fuel-specific infrastructure, they do not eliminate the complexities of integrating diverse energy sources or managing fluctuating supply and demand. Their viability also hinges on generating sufficient throughput and surplus energy - conditions not guaranteed for all SMPs [89], [91].

3) Enabling part-load consolidation concepts to reduce logistical inefficiencies and transport waste by the implementation of Mobile Distribution Centre (MDCs). The MDC concept addresses the inefficiency challenges through a flexible, decentralised model that enhances asset utilisation. By enabling shared container space among shippers and supporting both consolidation and distribution, MDCs improve fill rates across transport modes [109], [110], [111]. Their adaptable deployment overcome spatial and temporal mismatches that hinder traditional consolidation [111], [114], [115], [117]. MDCs also support dual-cycling, allowing return logistics like reusable packaging and waste collection, thus promoting circular logistics and sustainability [108]. Their modular design integrates with existing port and intermodal infrastructure, reducing cross-docking needs and enabling rapid deployment [109], [110], [111]. However, MDC effectiveness depends on commercial cooperation, digital coordination, and harmonised schedules - areas that have historically limited consolidation [111]. Asynchronous cargo availability and time-sensitive deliveries may also restrict MDC use in high-speed or high-value supply chains [86][87]. Moreover, transitioning to decentralised logistics requires cultural and operational shifts, which may face resistance without clear incentives or regulatory support [116].

While the study maps out overarching problems and potential solutions, its findings has its limitations, which calls for further investigation. First, the proposed conceptualisations were not developed in detail, nor scrutinized in terms of what technical solutions would be optimal in different settings. Furthermore, their application in an actual transport system should be evaluated to better understand the impact, in more quantitative terms, of deploying them. These aspects, along with others, are expected to be addressed within the AUTOFLEX project [33].

Acknowledgements

The research leading to the results presented in this research article has received funding from the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme, Horizon Europe, under Grant Agreement No. 101136257 (AUTOFLEX) and from the EFRE.NRW (2014-2020) Joint Research Funding Programme under grant agreement EFRE-0801222 (ML-2-1-010A, DeConTrans).

References

- [1] European Commission, 'The European Green Deal', The European Green Deal. Accessed: Nov. 17, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en
- [2] European Commission, 'Fit for 55', Consilium. Accessed: Jun. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/fit-for-55/>
- [3] Eurostat, 'Freight transport statistics - modal split'. European Commission, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Freight_transport_statistics_-_modal_split
- [4] N. Calderón-Rivera, I. Bartusevičienė, and F. Ballini, 'Sustainable development of inland waterways transport: a review', *J. Shipp. trd.*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2024, doi: 10.1186/s41072-023-00162-9.
- [5] J. Takman and M. Gonzalez-Aregall, 'Public policy instruments to promote freight modal shift in Europe: evidence from evaluations', *Transport Reviews*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 612-633, May 2024, doi: 10.1080/01441647.2023.2279219.
- [6] L. Björk, I. Vierth, and K. Cullinane, 'Freight modal shift: A means or an objective in achieving lower emission targets? The case of Sweden', *Transport Policy*, vol. 142, pp. 125-136, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tranpol.2023.08.013.
- [7] H. Dyrhaug and T. Rayner, 'Chapter 21: Transport: evolving EU policy towards a "hard-to-abate" sector',

- Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, 2023, pp. 305–320. doi: 10.4337/9781789906981.00035.
- [8] T. P. V. Zis, H. N. Psaraftis, G. Panagakos, and J. Kronbak, 'Policy measures to avert possible modal shifts caused by sulphur regulation in the European Ro-Ro sector', *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 70, pp. 1–17, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2019.03.001.
- [9] F. Simonelli *et al.*, 'New freight transport incentive to achieve modal shift targets: Methodology and application to Italy', *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, vol. 26, p. 101166, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.trip.2024.101166.
- [10] H. van Essen *et al.*, 'Handbook on the External Costs of Transport'. Publications Office for the European Union, Brussels, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9781f65f-8448-11ea-bf12-01aa75ed71a1>
- [11] European Commission, *Transport in the European Union – Current trends and issues*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2024. doi: 10.2832/131741.
- [12] J. Küchle and R. Fiedler, 'AUTOFLEX Deliverable D2.2: Market_Analysis', Fraunhofer CML, D2.2, Jan. 2025.
- [13] F. Bu and H. Nachtmann, 'Literature review and comparative analysis of inland waterways transport: "Container on Barge"', *Marit Econ Logist*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 140–173, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1057/s41278-021-00195-6.
- [14] C. Hendrickx and T. Breemersch, 'The Effect of Climate Change on Inland Waterway Transport', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 48, pp. 1837–1847, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.1158.
- [15] O. Jonkeren, B. Jourquin, and P. Rietveld, 'Modal-split effects of climate change: The effect of low water levels on the competitive position of inland waterway transport in the river Rhine area', *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, vol. 45, no. 10, pp. 1007–1019, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.tra.2009.01.004.
- [16] F. Vinke, M. van Koningsveld, C. van Dorsser, F. Baart, P. van Gelder, and T. Vellinga, 'Cascading effects of sustained low water on inland shipping', *Climate Risk Management*, vol. 35, p. 100400, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.crm.2022.100400.
- [17] C. Alias, E. van Hassel, D. Gründer, J. zum Felde, and L. Samuel, 'Investigating into the challenges of European inland ports: A multifaceted approach', *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 72, pp. 704–711, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2023.11.458.
- [18] L. Heilig and S. Voß, 'Inter-terminal transportation: an annotated bibliography and research agenda', *Flexible Services and Manufacturing Journal*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 35–63, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s10696-016-9237-7.
- [19] V. Pencheva, A. Asenov, A. Sladkowski, B. Ivanov, and I. Georgiev, 'Current Issues of Multimodal and Intermodal Cargo Transportation', in *Modern Trends and Research in Intermodal Transportation*, A. Sladkowski, Ed., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 51–124. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-87120-8_2.
- [20] D. Meers, C. Macharis, T. Vermeiren, and T. van Lier, 'Modal choice preferences in short-distance hinterland container transport', *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, vol. 23, pp. 46–53, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rtbm.2017.02.011.
- [21] B. Wiegmans and R. Konings, 'Intermodal Inland Waterway Transport: Modelling Conditions Influencing Its Cost Competitiveness', *The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 273–294, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ajsl.2015.06.006.
- [22] J. Weisheit, 'AUTOFLEX Homepage'. 2024. Accessed: Jun. 12, 2024. [Online]. Available: www.autoflex-vessel.eu
- [23] I. Bačkalov *et al.*, 'Impact of automation and zero-emission propulsion on design of small inland cargo vessels', *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2867, no. 1, p. 012018, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2867/1/012018.
- [24] J. S. Håvardsholm, 'Reach Subsea confirms delivery of Reach Remote 1', Reach Subsea. Accessed: Feb. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://reachsubsea.no/reach-subsea-confirms-delivery-of-reach-remote-1/>
- [25] R. O'Dwyer, 'ASKO to build two autonomous vessels for Oslo fjord operations', Smart Maritime Network. Accessed: Feb. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://smartmaritimenetwork.com/2020/09/01/asko-to-build-two-autonomous-vessels-for-oslo-fjord-operations/>
- [26] Yara, 'Yara Birkeland | Yara International', Yara None. Accessed: Jun. 19, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.yara.com/news-and-media/media-library/press-kits/yara-birkeland-press-kit/>
- [27] C. Alias and J. Z. Felde, 'Evaluating the economic performance of a decentralized waterborne container transportation service using autonomous inland vessels', presented at the IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems, Proceedings, ITSC, 2022, pp. 3571–3576. doi: 10.1109/ITSC55140.2022.9922500.
- [28] L. Kretschmann, H.-C. Burmeister, and C. Jahn, 'Analyzing the economic benefit of unmanned autonomous ships: An exploratory cost-comparison between an autonomous and a conventional bulk carrier', *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, vol. 25, pp. 76–86, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rtbm.2017.06.002.
- [29] E. Verbergh and E. van Hassel, 'The automated and unmanned inland vessel', *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.*, vol. 1357, no. 1, p. 012008, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1357/1/012008.
- [30] V. Gribkovskaia, H. Borgen, E. A. Holte, E. Lindstad, and H. Nordahl, 'Autonomous ships for coastal and short-sea shipping', presented at the SNAME Maritime Convention, OnePetro, Oct. 2019. Accessed: Jun. 19, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/>
- [31] K. Kloch and J. N. Kristiansen, 'The economic and environmental viability of green and autonomous ships in inland shipping ecosystems', in *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, Institute of Physics, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2867/1/012030.

- [32] C. Alias *et al.*, 'Design parameters, boundary conditions, model for logistics analysis defined', AUTOFLEX, Online, Deliverable D2.1, Dec. 2024. [Online]. Available: https://autoflex-vessel.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/AUTOFLEX_D2.1_Design-Basis.pdf
- [33] AUTOFLEX, 'AUTOFLEX | Partner | Consortium Overview'. Accessed: Jun. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://autoflex-vessel.eu/partner/>
- [34] A. McKinnon, 'Broadening the Scope of Decarbonization in the Maritime Sector', in *Maritime Decarbonization: Practical Tools, Case Studies and Decarbonization Enablers*, M. Lind, W. Lehmacher, and R. Ward, Eds., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023, pp. 3–15. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-39936-7_1.
- [35] A. McKinnon, *Decarbonizing Logistics: Distributing Goods in a Low Carbon World*, 1st ed. London, New York, New Delhi: Kogan Page, 2018.
- [36] I. Bačkalov *et al.*, '[D4.1] Design Impacts', Funded by the European Union (grant agreement No. 101136257), D4.1, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://autoflex-vessel.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/AUTOFLEX_Deliverable_4.1_Design_impacts_rev1.0.pdf
- [37] I. Bačkalov *et al.*, 'Impact of automation and zero-emission propulsion on design of small inland cargo vessels', presented at the Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2867/1/012018.
- [38] D. Mateienko *et al.*, '[D4.2] Uncrewed Vessel Concept', Funded by the European Union (grant agreement No. 101136257), D4.2, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://autoflex-vessel.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/101136257_AUTOFLEX_D4.2_Uncrewed-vessel-concept.pdf
- [39] J. F. Campbell, 'Freight consolidation and routing with transportation economies of scale', *Transp. Res. Part B Methodol.*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 345–361, 1990, doi: 10.1016/0191-2615(90)90008-M.
- [40] L. Fan and J. Xie, 'Identify determinants of container ship size investment choice', *Marit. Policy Manage.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 219–234, 2023, doi: 10.1080/03088839.2021.1971784.
- [41] N. K. Tran and H.-D. Haasis, 'An empirical study of fleet expansion and growth of ship size in container liner shipping', *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 159, pp. 241–253, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2014.09.016.
- [42] H. E. Haralambides, 'Gigantism in container shipping, ports and global logistics: a time-lapse into the future', *Maritime Economics and Logistics*, vol. 21, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1057/s41278-018-00116-0.
- [43] F. Lian, Jin Jiaru, and Z. and Yang, 'Optimal container ship size: a global cost minimization approach', *Maritime Policy & Management*, vol. 46, no. 7, pp. 802–817, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1080/03088839.2019.1630760.
- [44] H. Lindstad, B. E. Asbjørnslett, and A. H. Strømman, 'The importance of economies of scale for reductions in greenhouse gas emissions from shipping', *Energy Policy*, vol. 46, pp. 386–398, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2012.03.077.
- [45] U. Malchow, 'Growth in containership sizes to be stopped?', *Maritime Business Review*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 199–210, 2017, doi: 10.1108/MABR-01-2017-0001.
- [46] J. Garrido, S. Sauri, Á. Marrero, U. Gül, and C. Rúa, 'Predicting the future capacity and dimensions of container ships', *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2674, no. 9, pp. 177–190, 2020, doi: 10.1177/0361198120927395.
- [47] Alphaliner, 'Alphaliner TOP 100 / 16 Jun 2025'. Accessed: Jun. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://alphaliner.axsmarine.com/PublicTop100/>
- [48] H. Deiss, 'The recomposition of the shipping alliances in 2025', *Apply Transportation & Logistics Analysis*. Accessed: Jun. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://market-insights.apply.com/en/the-recomposition-of-the-shipping-alliances-in-2025>
- [49] M. Ghorbani, M. Acciaro, S. Transchel, and P. Cariou, 'Strategic alliances in container shipping: A review of the literature and future research agenda', *Marit. Econ. Logist.*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 439–465, 2022, doi: 10.1057/s41278-021-00205-7.
- [50] S. Caschili, F. Medda, F. Parola, and C. Ferrari, 'An Analysis of Shipping Agreements: The Cooperative Container Network', *Netw. Spat. Econ.*, vol. 14, no. 3–4, pp. 357–377, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s11067-014-9230-1.
- [51] J.-P. Rodrigue, *The Geography of Transport Systems*, 5th ed. New York: Routledge, 2020.
- [52] ITF, 'The Impact of Mega-Ships', OECD Publishing, Paris, No. 10, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jlwvzcm3j9v-en>.
- [53] M. Acciaro and A. McKinnon, 'Efficient Hinterland Transport Infrastructure and Services for Large Container Ports', OECD Publishing, Paris, Working paper No. 2013/19, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jz40sclnwf4-en>
- [54] K. Cullinane and M. Khanna, 'Economies of scale in large containerships: Optimal size and geographical implications', *J. Transp. Geogr.*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 181–195, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0966-6923(00)00010-7.
- [55] L. Feng and T. Notteboom, 'Peripheral challenge by Small and Medium Sized Ports (SMPs) in Multi-Port Gateway Regions: the case study of northeast of China', *Polish Maritime Research*, vol. 20, no. Special-Issue, pp. 55–66, 2013, doi: 10.2478/pomr-2013-0027.
- [56] L. Gerlitz and C. Meyer, 'Small and medium-sized ports in the ten-t network and nexus of europe's twin transition: The way towards sustainable and digital port service ecosystems', *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 8, 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13084386.
- [57] J.-P. Rodrigue and T. Notteboom, 'The terminalization of supply chains: reassessing the role of terminals in

- port/hinterland logistical relationships', *Maritime Policy & Management*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 165–183, Apr. 2009, doi: 10.1080/03088830902861086.
- [58] M. Fugazza and J. Hoffmann, 'Liner shipping connectivity as determinant of trade', *Journal of Shipping and Trade*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 1, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1186/s41072-017-0019-5.
- [59] V. Santén, S. Rogerson, J. Williamsson, and J. Woxenius, 'Modal shift to inland waterway transport: Five case studies in the North Sea Region', *EJTIR*, vol. 21, no. 4, 2021, doi: 10.18757/ejtir.2021.21.4.5474.
- [60] C. Ducruet and D. Guerrero, 'Inland cities, maritime gateways, and international trade', *Journal of Transport Geography*, vol. 104, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2022.103433.
- [61] T. Platz and G. Klatt, 'The role of inland waterway transport in the changing logistics environment', in *Inland Waterway Transport: Challenges and Prospects*, Taylor and Francis, 2016, pp. 35–70. doi: 10.4324/9781315739083.
- [62] B. Wiśnicki, D. Dybkowska-Stefek, J. Relisko-Rybak, and Ł. Kolanda, 'Methodology for determining the location of river ports on a modernized waterway based on non-cost criteria: A case study of the odra river waterway', *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 6, 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13063571.
- [63] O. Jonkeren, J. Francke, and J. Visser, 'A shift-share based tool for assessing the contribution of a modal shift to the decarbonisation of inland freight transport', *Eur. Transp. Res. Rev.*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2019, doi: 10.1186/s12544-019-0344-x.
- [64] S. Damman, M. Wardeberg, and C. Gabriellii, 'Policies shaping energy transitions in ports and harbours: A "whole systems" perspective from Norway', *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.*, vol. 125, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2025.104101.
- [65] D. A. Nesheim, J. N. Kristiansen, J. Raakjaer, and O. E. Morkrid, 'The Need for Collaborative Business Models in Autonomous Vessel Ecosystems', in *The 4th International Conference on Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (ICMASS)*, in Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 2311. Singapore: IOP Press, Apr. 2022.
- [66] A. Vilarinho, L. B. Liboni, and J. Siegler, 'Challenges and opportunities for the development of river logistics as a sustainable alternative: A systematic review', in *Transp. Res. Procedia*, Thompson R.G., Iwan S., and Kijewska K., Eds., Elsevier B.V., 2019, pp. 576–586. doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2019.06.059.
- [67] A. Caris, S. Limbourg, C. Macharis, T. van Lier, and M. Cools, 'Integration of inland waterway transport in the intermodal supply chain: A taxonomy of research challenges', *J. Transp. Geogr.*, vol. 41, pp. 126–136, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2014.08.022.
- [68] A. Grobarcikova and J. Sosedová, 'Design of agent-based model for barge container transport', *Transport Problems*, vol. 11, pp. 95–101, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.20858/tp.2016.11.4.9.
- [69] M. Akhavan, 'Decarbonising Maritime Transport: The Role of Green Shipping Corridors in Making Sustainable Port-City Ecosystems', *OaS*, vol. 2, p. 9411, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.17645/oas.9411.
- [70] A. M. Ismail, F. Ballini, A. I. Ölçer, and A. S. Alamoush, 'Integrating ports into green shipping corridors: Drivers, challenges, and pathways to implementation', *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 209, p. 117201, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.117201.
- [71] J. B. Svendsen, E. Petit, M. Selwyn, and A. K. Bjerregaard, 'Establishing Green Shipping Corridors to Accelerate the Use of Alternative Fuels', in *Maritime Decarbonization*, M. Lind, W. Lehmacher, and R. Ward, Eds., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023, pp. 433–449. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-39936-7_31.
- [72] L. van der Lugt, 'Port development company: Role and strategy', in *Ports and Networks: Strategies, Operations and Perspectives*, 2017, pp. 54–66. doi: 10.4324/9781315601540.
- [73] J.-F. Ding, Kuo Jung-Fong, Shyu Wen-Hwa, and C.-C. and Chou, 'Evaluating determinants of attractiveness and their cause-effect relationships for container ports in Taiwan: users' perspectives', *Maritime Policy & Management*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 466–490, May 2019, doi: 10.1080/03088839.2018.1562245.
- [74] S. Lim, S. Pettit, W. Abouarghoub, and A. Beresford, 'Port sustainability and performance: A systematic literature review', *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.*, vol. 72, pp. 47–64, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2019.04.009.
- [75] F. Parola, Risitano, Marcello, Ferretti, Marco, and E. and Panetti, 'The drivers of port competitiveness: a critical review', *Transport Reviews*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 116–138, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1080/01441647.2016.1231232.
- [76] P. W. de Langen, 'The strategy of the port development company; a framework based on the business ecosystems perspective and an application to the case of Port of Rotterdam', *Maritime Transport Research*, vol. 4, p. 100089, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.martra.2023.100089.
- [77] S. Damman and M. Steen, 'A socio-technical perspective on the scope for ports to enable energy transition', *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.*, vol. 91, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2020.102691.
- [78] T. Notteboom and H. Haralambides, 'Seaports as green hydrogen hubs: advances, opportunities and challenges in Europe', *Marit. Econ. Logist.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 1–27, 2023, doi: 10.1057/s41278-023-00253-1.
- [79] W. Monteith and V. B. Escobar, 'Speculative connections: Port authorities, littoral territories and the assembling of the green hydrogen frontier', *Political Geography*, vol. 118, p. 103271, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.polgeo.2025.103271.
- [80] M. Flikkema et al., 'MAGPIE: Towards the European Green port of the Future', *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 72, pp. 187–194, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2023.11.393.
- [81] M. Klopott, M. Popek, and I. Urbanyi-Popiołek, 'Seaports' Role in Ensuring the Availability of Alternative Marine Fuels—A Multi-Faceted Analysis', *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 7, 2023, doi: 10.3390/en16073055.

- [82] G. Barone *et al.*, 'Steering shipping towards energy sustainability: alternative fuels in decarbonization policies', *Energy*, vol. 331, p. 136827, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2025.136827.
- [83] A. T. Hoang *et al.*, 'Energy-related approach for reduction of CO2 emissions: A critical strategy on the port-to-ship pathway', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 355, p. 131772, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131772.
- [84] Ç. Iris and J. S. L. Lam, 'A review of energy efficiency in ports: Operational strategies, technologies and energy management systems', *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev*, vol. 112, pp. 170–182, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.04.069.
- [85] T. Andra Luciana, C. Gasparotti, and E. Rusu, 'Green fuels — A new challenge for marine industry', *Energy Reports*, vol. 7, pp. 127–132, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.06.020.
- [86] S. Yu, Z. Huang, D. Tang, W. Ma, and J. M. Guerrero, 'The Role of Integrated Multi-Energy Systems Toward Carbon-Neutral Ports: A Data-Driven Approach Using Empirical Data', *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2025, doi: 10.3390/jmse13030477.
- [87] S. A. Alavi-Borazjani, S. Adeel, and V. Chkoniya, 'Hydrogen as a Sustainable Fuel: Transforming Maritime Logistics', *Energies*, vol. 18, no. 5, 2025, doi: 10.3390/en18051231.
- [88] H. Sornn-Friese *et al.*, *Ports as Energy Transition Hubs: An Exploratory Study*, 1st ed. Copenhagen: CBS Maritime, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://research-api.cbs.dk/ws/portalfiles/portal/110673309/ports_as_energy_transition_hubs_an_exploratory_study.pdf
- [89] J. Monios, G. Wilmsmeier, G. A. M. Tello, and L. Pomaska, 'A new conception of port governance under climate change', *J. Transp. Geogr.*, vol. 120, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2024.103988.
- [90] G. Attanasio, C. Battistella, and E. Chizzolini, 'The future of energy management: Results of a Delphi panel applied in the case of ports', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 417, p. 137947, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137947.
- [91] M. Acciaro, H. Ghiara, and M. I. Cusano, 'Energy management in seaports: A new role for port authorities', *Energy Policy*, vol. 71, pp. 4–12, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2014.04.013.
- [92] W. Lu, S. H. Park, J. G. Oh, and G. T. Yeo, 'Network Connection Strategy for Small and Medium-sized Ports (SMPs)', *The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 19–26, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ajsl.2018.03.003.
- [93] I. Argyriou and T. Tsoutsos, 'Sustainable Solutions for Small/Medium Ports a Guide to Efficient and Effective Planning', *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 9, 2023, doi: 10.3390/jmse11091763.
- [94] C. Meyer, L. Gerlitz, and G. Prause, 'Smart City and Smart Port Concepts: A Conceptualisation for Digital Small and Medium-Sized Port-City Innovation Ecosystems', in *Reliability and Statistics in Transportation and Communication*, I. Kabashkin, I. Yatskiv, and O. Prentkovskis, Eds., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 41–53.
- [95] Peter Bjerg Olesen, Iskra Dukovska-Popovska, Hans-Henrik Hvolby, and Kenn Steger-Jensen, 'Strategic port development: Identifying a development approach for small and medium-sized ports', *Danish Journal of Transportation Research - Dansk tidsskrift for transportforskning*, vol. 2012, p. 16, 2012.
- [96] M. Gonzalez Aregall, R. Bergqvist, and J. Monios, 'A global review of the hinterland dimension of green port strategies', *Transp. Res. Part D Transp. Environ.*, vol. 59, pp. 23–34, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2017.12.013.
- [97] N. Safara Nosar, 'Unraveling interactions: Mechanisms shaping the transition of small and medium-sized ports to energy hubs', *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.*, vol. 31, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.trip.2025.101417.
- [98] E. Vichos, N. Sifakis, and T. Tsoutsos, 'Challenges of integrating hydrogen energy storage systems into nearly zero-energy ports', *Energy*, vol. 241, p. 122878, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.122878.
- [99] F. Bedoya-Maya, J. Beckers, and E. van Hassel, 'Spillover effects from inland waterway transport development: Spatial assessment of the Rhine-Alpine Corridor', *J. Transp. Geogr.*, vol. 113, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2023.103721.
- [100] Eurostat, 'Road freight transport by journey characteristics', European Union, Brussels, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Road_freight_transport_by_journey_characteristics#Empty_runnings_of_road_freight_vehicles
- [101] Eurostat, 'Road freight transport by vehicle characteristics', European Union, Brussels, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Road_freight_transport_by_vehicle_characteristics#Road_freight_transport_by_load_capacity
- [102] A. Abdelshafie, M. Salah, T. Kramberger, and D. Dragan, 'Repositioning and Optimal Re-Allocation of Empty Containers: A Review of Methods, Models, and Applications', *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 11, p. 6655, May 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14116655.
- [103] U. Sanders, J. Riedl, L. Kloppsteck, C. Roeloffs, and J. Schlingmeier, 'Think Outside Your Boxes: Solving the Global Container-Repositioning Puzzle', BCG Operations. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2015/transportation-travel-logistics-think-outside-your-boxes-solving-global-container-repositioning-puzzle>
- [104] United Nations, 'Review of maritime transport 2024: Navigating maritime chokepoints', United Nations, New York, NY (USA), 2024. [Online]. Available: https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2024_en.pdf

- [105] Eurostat, 'Maritime transport statistics - short sea shipping of goods', Statistics Explained. Accessed: Jun. 21, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Maritime_transport_statistics_-_short_sea_shipping_of_goods
- [106] Flexport, 'Filling Underutilized Ocean Containers', *Forbes*, 2019. Accessed: Jun. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/flexport/2019/05/01/filling-underutilized-ocean-containers/>
- [107] S. Pan, E. Ballot, and F. Fontane, 'The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from freight transport by pooling supply chains', *Int J Prod Econ*, vol. 143, no. 1, pp. 86–94, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2010.10.023.
- [108] COWI, 'Analysis of Recent Trends in EU Shipping and Analysis and Policy Support to Improve the Competitiveness of Short Sea Shipping in the EU', European Commission, DG Mobility and Transport, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-09/2015-june-study-sss-final.pdf>
- [109] F. Bedoya-Maya *et al.*, 'Cargo consolidation in port-hinterland container transport: A spatial economic assessment for inland waterways', *Research in Transportation Business and Management*, vol. 59, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.rtbm.2024.101254.
- [110] Y. Fan, B. Behdani, J. Bloemhof-Ruwaard, and R. Zuidwijk, 'Flow consolidation in hinterland container transport: An analysis for perishable and dry cargo', *Transp. Res. Part E Logist. Transp. Rev.*, vol. 130, pp. 128–160, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tre.2019.08.011.
- [111] M. van der Horst, M. Kort, B. Kuipers, and H. Geerlings, 'Coordination problems in container barging in the port of Rotterdam: an institutional analysis', *Transportation Planning and Technology*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 187–199, 2019, doi: 10.1080/03081060.2019.1565164.
- [112] K. J. Galambos, A. B. Palomino-Hernández, V. C. Hemmelmayr, and B. Turan, 'Sustainability initiatives in urban freight transportation in Europe', *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.*, vol. 23, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.trip.2023.101013.
- [113] T. Letnik, M. Marksel, G. Luppino, A. Bardi, and S. Božičnik, 'Review of policies and measures for sustainable and energy efficient urban transport', *Energy*, vol. 163, pp. 245–257, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.08.096.
- [114] M. Faccio and M. Gamberi, 'New city logistics paradigm: From the "Last Mile" to the "Last 50 Miles" sustainable distribution', *Sustainability*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 14873–14894, 2015, doi: 10.3390/su71114873.
- [115] K. Katsela, Ş. Güneş, T. Fried, A. Goodchild, and M. Browne, 'Defining Urban Freight Microhubs: A Case Study Analysis', *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14010532.
- [116] P. Lebeau, S. Verlinde, C. Macharis, and J. Van Mierlo, 'How can authorities support urban consolidation centres? A review of the accompanying measures', *J. Urban.*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 468–486, 2017, doi: 10.1080/17549175.2017.1310747.
- [117] R. Dekker, J. Bloemhof, and I. Mallidis, 'Operations Research for green logistics – An overview of aspects, issues, contributions and challenges', *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 219, no. 3, pp. 671–679, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.ejor.2011.11.010.
- [118] V. Bernhardsson, 'Representation of the Swedish transport and logistics system in Samgods 1.2.2', TMALL 0004 Rapport generell v 2.0, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://bransch.trafikverket.se/contentassets/ab220f9016154ef7a847855560bb280/2024/representation-of-the-swedish-transport-and-logistics-system-in-samgods-1.2.2.pdf>
- [119] M. Browne, J. Woexenius, L. Dablanc, T. Cherrett, and E. Morganti, 'Port cities and urban logistics', LRN 2017 Papers. Accessed: Aug. 12, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ciltuk.org.uk/About-Us/Professional-Sectors-Forums/Forums/LRN-Forum>
- [120] C. Hein and P. Th. Van De Laar, 'The Separation of Ports from Cities: The Case of Rotterdam', in *European Port Cities in Transition*, A. Carpenter and R. Lozano, Eds., in Strategies for Sustainability. , Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 265–286. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-36464-9_15.
- [121] G. Balletto, G. Borruso, and T. Campisi, 'Not Only Waterfront. The Port-City Relations Between Peripheries and Inner Harbors', in *Computational Science and Its Applications – ICCSA 2022 Workshops*, O. Gervasi, B. Murgante, S. Misra, A. M. A. C. Rocha, and C. Garau, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 196–208. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-10548-7_15.